

22NRM01 TraMeXI

D8 - Draft B comparison report for supplementary comparison for X-ray tube voltage calibrations in X-ray imaging reference radiation qualities submitted to EURAMET TC IR

Organisation name of the lead participant for the deliverable: INM

Due date of the deliverable: 05-2026

Actual submission date of the deliverable: 05-2026

Confidentiality Status: PU - Public, fully open (remember to deposit public deliverables in a trusted repository)

Deliverable Cover Sheet

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The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

European Partnership Co-funded by the European Union

**METROLOGY
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Glossary

CMC	Calibration and measurement capability
KCDB	BIPM key comparison database
RQR	General radiography reference radiation qualities defined in IEC standard IEC 61267
RQT	Computed tomography reference radiation qualities defined in IEC standard IEC 61267
XMM	X-ray multimeter

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1 Summary

EURAMET supplementary comparisons (EURAMET.RI(1)-S20) was conducted to assess the calibration and measurement capabilities of ten European national metrology laboratories for peak tube voltage quantity relevant to medical x-ray imaging [1]. The comparisons were performed between November 2024 and December 2025. Three x-ray multimeters (XMMs) served as transfer instruments for tube voltage. The comparisons covered conventional RQR radiation qualities [2].

Because no BIPM key comparisons exist for the radiation qualities or quantities included, no degrees of equivalence were determined [3, 4]. Instead, comparison reference values were established as the weighted mean of results from participants utilizing primary measurement methods [5]. For tube voltage the traceability was based on spectrometric realization or traceable high-voltage divider systems. The behaviour of the transfer instruments, including their stability during transport, was evaluated through repeated measurements at the pilot laboratory and for XMMs additional information available by manufacturer specifications, in IEC standards [6] and information obtained within the TraMeXI-project [7].

For EURAMET.RI(1)-S20, tube voltage, the use of XMMs, whose internal algorithms and uncertainty contributions were studied concurrently within the TraMeXI-project, introduced larger variability due to differences in measurement conditions affecting the transfer instruments. To compensate for these effects additional uncertainty components reflecting these variabilities were introduced for the purposes of this comparison. For EURAMET.RI(1)-S20, tube voltage, the results show consistency across all radiation qualities, with all participants achieving $|En| \leq 1$.

Overall, the comparisons confirm that the participating laboratories have capabilities to provide reliable and comparable calibration services for both tube voltage. The results support the maintenance or establishment of CMC entries in the KCDB [8].

2 Proof of submission

The comparison report has been sent to the EURAMET TC-IR chair (Figure 1). The comparison report will be reviewed following the CCRI rules and when approved, it will be published in the KCDB.

Supplementary comparison report EURAMET.RI(I)-S20 and -S21

Dear Linda,

I am happy to send you, as the TC-IR chair, the report covering the supplementary comparisons on tube voltage, EURAMET.RI(I)-S20 and air kerma, EURAMET.RI(I)-S21. These comparisons are linked to the TraMeXI project. All participants have reviewed and agreed with the report. We have made our best to bring it to a good level, and we hope that you will find it acceptable. Could you please confirm receipt of the report? We would also be grateful for any comments or requests you may have.

Best regards,
Paula

Figure 1. The comparison report was sent by email to the EURAMET TC-IR chair for approval.

References

- [1] EURAMET.RI(I).S20 Comparison of tube voltage for x-ray imaging 2026. <https://www.bipm.org/kcdb/comparison?id=1973> (accessed May 7, 2026).
- [2] International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC). Medical diagnostic X-ray equipment - Radiation conditions for use in the determination of characteristics, IEC 61267:2025. 2025.
- [3] CIPM. Measurement comparisons in the CIPM MRA, CIPM MRA-D-05. Sèvres, Paris: 2016.
- [4] EURAMET. Guide No. 4: Guide on comparisons. Braunschweig: 2021.
- [5] International Organization for Standardization. Statistical methods for use in proficiency testing by interlaboratory comparison. Geneva: 2022.
- [6] International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC). Medical electrical equipment – Dosimetric instruments used for non invasive measurement of X ray tube voltage in diagnostic radiology, 2023, IEC 61676:2023. Geneva: 2023.
- [7] Krzanovic N, Toroi P, Komatina I, Jansen B, Boziari A, Caldeira M, de Castro M C, Ciccotelli A, Fernandes A, Kojic A, Lee K, Lindholm C, Pojtinger S, Reyhanoglu E, Rinaldi L, Sabeta A, Salomon E, Saroka S, Silvestri C, Sochor V, Valkama V, Vlahovic J and Zivanovic M. 2026 X-ray imaging dosimeter performance in standard and non-standard radiography radiation fields in terms of air kerma. Phys Med 2026;141:105687. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmp.2025.105687>
- [8] BIPM. KCDB The BIPM Key Comparison Database is available online 2019. <https://www.bipm.org/kcdb/> (accessed May 6, 2019).